

Pairwise-Elo Rating System

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Abstract

This paper proposes a statistical model for players' pairwise advantages by extending the de facto Elo rating system. While various rating systems have been proposed, almost all rating systems assume that players' ratings are totally ordered, and transitivity holds. Such assumption precludes possibilities that a specific player plays very well against another specific player regardless of their general ability. The proposed model consists of (i) a statistical test for the existence of pairwise advantages (i.e. existence of intransitivity) for the entire group of players and (ii) estimation of winning probability for each of the pairs with the inclusion of pairwise advantage. We call our model P-Elo model. We will compare P-Elo model to the traditional Elo rating system on sports: Sumo Wrestling (Sumo) and Mixed Martial Art (MMA); as well as StarCraft II (SC2), and the recently popular Large Language Model (LLM) evaluation in terms of match/comparison result prediction and probability estimation.

Key Words: Elo Rating System, Bradley-Terry model, Pairwise Comparison, Ranking Systems, Statistical modelling, Hypothesis Testing, Time Series, Sports forecasting, Large Language Model

1. Introduction

The Elo rating system, introduced by Arpad Elo [10], is widely used in various domains, such as ranking players in zero-sum games like chess [28], individual/team sports like pool [13] and football [20][14], ranking scientific journals [27], and tracking dominance in dynamic animal systems [31]. Elo assumes that the probability of player i defeating player j depends on the difference in their ratings through a logistic function [10]. After each game, ratings are updated as $R_i \leftarrow R_i + K(X - p_{ij})$, where X is the binary result ($0 = \text{loss}$, $1 = \text{win}$), p_{ij} is the win probability, and K controls update speed. Larger K makes ratings respond quickly but unstable, while smaller K yields slower, more stable updates.

The Bradley-Terry model [5] generalizes Elo, estimating static player strengths via maximum likelihood. Elo can be seen as an online, dynamic version, updating ratings sequentially. Extensions include using Elo for sports predictions like tennis [25][26], where Margin of Victory (MoV) replaces binary outcomes [26]. In Go, factors like offensiveness are included [35]. Elo has even been used to rank large language models (LLMs) [8], later replaced by Bradley-Terry as LLMs are assumed to have constant true strengths [7].

Time-varying player abilities have been studied with time series approaches. Aldous [1] examined Elo's limitations, while Fahrmeir [12] and Duffield [9] developed non-Gaussian state-space models. Statistically, Elo resembles a binary time-series model with parameter K . The GARCH model [11][4] offers insights for modeling variability and intransitivity.

Some researchers extend the Elo rating system through Bayesian approach. The Glicko system [15][16][17] improves Elo by introducing Ratings Deviation (RD), adjusting update speed based on information availability, and developed closed form formulas as update rules for ratings. Microsoft's TrueSkill [19] is a full Bayesian method for multiplayer games, later evolving into TrueSkill2 [30] with added behavioral factors.

Classic Elo assumes transitivity: if player 1 beats player 2 and player 2 beats player 3, player 1 should beat player 3. However, this often fails in practice, as seen with left-handed fencers’ advantage over right-handers. When transitivity breaks down, Bradley-Terry/Elo models are invalid [36]. Models like Blade-Chest [6], generalized Blade-Chest [18], mElo2k [2], and Disc Decomposition [3] address intransitivity by adding parameters, improving predictions for some games (e.g., StarCraft II) but not others (e.g., tennis). These models assume static strengths and have high parameter counts. Maystre [29] introduced a dynamic model using Gaussian processes to relax transitivity, improving accuracy further.

We propose the **Pairwise-Elo (P-Elo)** model, extending Elo to include pair-specific strengths between players. This adds a parameter K_2 to model pairwise interactions. When transitivity holds, K dominates; when intransitivity is severe, K_2 dominates. P-Elo dynamically combines general and pair-specific performance, detecting intransitivity from data. It also allows formal testing of transitivity via likelihood ratio tests and simulations.

For comparison, a Bradley-Terry model with pairwise effects requires $n + \binom{n}{2}$ parameters for n players, making it impractical for large datasets. P-Elo is more parsimonious and robust, with only two parameters (K and K_2).

We evaluate P-Elo through simulation and apply it to four datasets: Sumo Wrestling, Mixed Martial Arts (MMA), StarCraft II, and LLM evaluation. We also explore a hypothetical sports betting scenario to test whether P-Elo outperforms classic Elo when transitivity fails.

While Bradley-Terry suits static-strength contexts like LLM ranking, sports require models with time-varying strengths, as player abilities change with age, experience, or team composition. Both Elo and Bradley-Terry assume transitivity, but real-world factors often violate this assumption. Alternative cumulative distribution functions (e.g., Probit, Cauchy) could replace the logistic function and handle some but not all kinds of intransitivity, though selecting the best fit remains challenging.

2. Classic Elo and P-Elo Rating Systems

2.1 Classic Elo Rating System

In the classic Elo rating system proposed by Elo [10], suppose the $(t + 1)^{th}$ game is player i vs player j , then the probability of player i with rating $R_{i,t}$ wins against player j with rating $R_{j,t}$ is a function of the difference in rating $R_{i,t} - R_{j,t}$, i.e. $p_{ij,t+1} = P(i \text{ wins } j \text{ in the } (t + 1)^{th} \text{ game}) = u(R_{i,t} - R_{j,t})$, u is chosen to be a logistic function. After the encounter, their ratings will be updated based on this probability $p_{ij,t+1}$, game result and a chosen parameter K , formulas provided below. If the true strength of player i and player j are constants, i.e. R_i and R_j respectively, then the probability $p_{ij,t+1}$ will converge to the true winning probability $p_{ij} = u(R_i - R_j)$, under the assumption that (1) any players could play against any players, (2) there are infinitely many games and (3) the choice of parameter K is small and close to zero [21]. For an appropriate (not necessarily small) choice of K , the distribution of the estimated probability has mean equal to the true probability which we will show in the simulation section. However, it is more realistic that the players’ abilities evolve over time: younger players get stronger, old player get weaker and players’ abilities fluctuate even within a relatively short time.

Under the classic Elo rating system:

$$p_{ij,t+1} = u(R_{i,t} - R_{j,t}) = \left(1 + 10^{-\frac{(R_{i,t} - R_{j,t})}{400}}\right)^{-1} \quad (\text{eq1})$$

Ratings of player i and player j will be updated according to (1) the game result, (2) the winning probabilities, and (3) an appropriate parameter $K > 0$,

$$R_{i,t+1} \leftarrow R_{i,t} + K(X_{t+1} - p_{ij,t+1}) \quad R_{j,t+1} \leftarrow R_{j,t} - K(X_{t+1} - p_{ij,t+1}) \quad (\text{eq2})$$

Classic Elo rating system assumes the game outcome X_t (1 = win, 0 = loss) only depends on the ratings of the two involved players i and j , therefore at any time t , $R_{i,t}$ (for all i) could be viewed as the unobservable variables driving the binary time series $\{X_t\}_{t \in [1,2,\dots,n]}$ where K is the only parameter involved in the model.

2.2 Pairwise-Elo (P-Elo) Rating System

In the classic Elo rating system, all players are totally ordered and the relationship among multiple winning probabilities are restricted. For example, suppose there are only 3 players in the player pool and two of the winning probabilities are known, i.e. $p_{12} = u(R_1 - R_2) = 0.6$ and $p_{23} = u(R_2 - R_3) = 0.6$. Then p_{13} is already determined:

$$p_{13} = \left(1 + 10^{-(R_1 - R_3)/400}\right)^{-1} = \left(1 + 10^{-((R_1 - R_2) + (R_2 - R_3))/400}\right)^{-1} \approx 0.69.$$

This is intuitively false because the performance of player 1 against player 3 should not solely depends on their performance against player 2. Also, there are no strong reasons that the logistic function determines the transitivity for certain data generating processes. In general, the relationship among winning probabilities should not be restricted. Moreover, if there exist pairwise strengths between any two players, the distribution of the estimated probability from classic Elo rating system does not have mean equal to the true probability, which we will show in a later section using simulation.

Motivated by the above example, building on the classic Elo rating system, we introduce $\binom{n}{2}$ time-varying pairwise strengths, between any two players. Let Q_t be the $n \times n$ matrix containing pairwise strengths up to game t ,

$$Q_t = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & q_{12,t} & \dots & q_{1n,t} \\ -q_{12,t} & 0 & \dots & q_{2n,t} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -q_{1n,t} & -q_{2n,t} & \dots & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$q_{21,t} = -q_{12,t}$ because of the symmetry between advantage and disadvantage. $q_{ij,t}$ can be introduced into formula (eq1), since now player i has pairwise advantage $q_{ij,t}$ on player j , we should replace $R_{i,t-1}$ by $R_{i,t-1} + q_{ij,t-1}$,

$$p_{ij,t+1} = u(R_{i,t} + q_{ij,t} - R_{j,t}) = \left(1 + 10^{-(R_{i,t} + q_{ij,t} - R_{j,t})/400}\right)^{-1} \quad (\text{eq3})$$

The update rules for $q_{ij,t}$ are similar to Classic Elo Rating, with $K_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ being another appropriate parameter to be estimated,

$$q_{ij,t+1} \leftarrow q_{ij,t} + K_2(X_{t+1} - p_{ij,t+1}) \quad (\text{eq4})$$

When $K_2 = 0$, P-Elo reduced to the classic Elo rating system.

P-Elo rating system hereby assumes the game outcome X_t depends not only on the ratings of the two involved players i and j , but it also depends on the pairwise strengths $q_{ij,t}$. Therefore, at any time t , $R_{i,t}$ and $q_{ij,t}$ (for all i and j) could be viewed as the $n + \binom{n}{2}$ observable ratings and pairwise strengths driving the process $\{X_t\}_{t \in [1,2,\dots,n]}$ where K and K_2 are the only parameters involved in the model.

3. The statistically significance of the parameter K_2 in P-Elo under Likelihood Ratio Test

Given a fixed game schedule and game results \bar{Y} , the likelihood under the classic Elo model with one parameter K is:

$$L_0(K|\bar{Y}) = \prod_{t=1}^n u(R_{i,t-1} - R_{j,t-1})Y_t + \left(1 - u(R_{i,t-1} - R_{j,t-1})\right) (1 - Y_t) \quad (\text{eq5})$$

Note that i, j are not fixed for each game. K in the update rule (eq2), not explicitly being shown on the right-hand side, determines how the ratings change over time and therefore dictates the probability of winning in each game, implying that K can be estimated by maximum likelihood. On the other hand, the likelihood under P-Elo model with two parameters K and K_2 is:

$$L_a(K, K_2|\bar{Y}) = \prod_{t=1}^n u\left(R_{i,t-1} + q_{ij,t-1} - R_{j,t-1}\right)Y_t + \left(1 - u\left(R_{i,t-1} + q_{ij,t-1} - R_{j,t-1}\right)\right) (1 - Y_t) \quad (\text{eq6})$$

Parameters K and K_2 in the update rules (eq2) and (eq4) determine how the ratings and pairwise strength change over time and therefore dictate the probability of winning in each game. Similarly, K and K_2 can be estimated by maximum likelihood. Under the hypothesis testing:

$$\begin{aligned} H_0 &: K > 0, K_2 = 0 \\ H_a &: K > 0, K_2 \neq 0 \end{aligned}$$

The test statistic of likelihood ratio test would be:

$$\lambda_n = -2 \log \left(\frac{\sup_{K \in \mathbb{R}^+} L_0(K|\bar{Y})}{\sup_{(K, K_2) \in \mathbb{R}^+ \times \mathbb{R}} L_a(K, K_2|\bar{Y})} \right) \sim \chi^2(1) \quad (\text{eq7})$$

Since ratings and pairwise strengths change over time, the winning probabilities are path dependent, i.e. a player with higher rating or pairwise strength against another player means this player is more likely to win the next game. Although the game results are not i.i.d., they are conditionally independent, i.e. given the current rating, the game result does not depend on any of the previous game results. The joint probability function of all games depends on all ratings and pairwise strengths, therefore, depends on the binary game results. In our case, likelihood ratio test is not directly applicable, but our conjecture is that λ_n still follows $\chi^2(1)$, Chi-Square distribution with 1 degree of freedom, asymptotically as $n \rightarrow \infty$. [32] [34] [33] We will use simulation to support this conjecture.

Hence, by likelihood ratio test, the null distribution of the test statistic is $\chi^2(1)$ and the rejection region is $\lambda_n \geq \chi_{1-\alpha}^2(1)$ where α is the significance level.

3.1 Null distribution: Chi-Square with 1 degree of freedom $\chi^2(1)$

To simulate the distribution of λ_n , we generate game result using $K \neq 0$ and $K_2 = 0$. We predetermined (1) how many players are in the player pool, (2) the initial ratings of the players and (3) how many games were played. The randomness of the simulation lies in the game pairings and game results. We assumed the players' ratings are players' true strengths, therefore the updated ratings after each game will be used to generate the next game result. We summarized the specification of the simulation below:

- $K \in \{0, 8, 16, 24, 32, 40, 48, 56, 64, 72, 80\}$, 11 different values of K
- $K_2 = 0$
- Number of players = 200
- Initial ratings of the players: randomized between 1,000 and 2,000
- Number of games played = 10,000
- Pairing: All-meet-all, with some players pairing up more frequently to mimic reality

We used one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test to examine the similarity between the distribution of λ_n and $\chi^2(1)$. Given K , the KS test is:

$H_0: \lambda_n$ follows $\chi^2(1)$

$H_1: \lambda_n$ does not follow $\chi^2(1)$

$\alpha = 0.05$

Result:

K	mean(λ_n)	var(λ_n)	p-value of KS test
0	1.03	2.05	0.29
8	0.99	1.96	0.79
16	1.07	1.94	0.03
24	1.07	2.18	0.09
32	1.01	2.07	0.37
40	0.99	2.19	0.99
48	0.93	1.85	0.69
56	1.00	2.08	0.76
64	1.06	2.15	0.26
72	0.95	1.64	0.86
80	0.98	1.96	0.61
Average	1.01	2.01	

Table 1: Simulation of λ_n , p-value of KS test

For each value of K , we used 1000 different seeds to get the distribution of λ_n . Table 1 summarizes the result, using 11 values of K and significance level $\alpha = 0.05$, the Bonferroni corrected p-value is $0.05/11 \approx 0.0045$. The result showed that there is no statistical evidence that λ_n does not follow $\chi^2(1)$ asymptotically. The mean and variance of the test statistic are 1.01 and 2.01 respectively which are close to the mean and variance of $\chi^2(1)$, i.e. $E(\chi^2(1)) = 1$ and $Var(\chi^2(1)) = 2$.

3.2 Power of the test

How likely is the test rejecting H_0 when K_2 is not zero? The test is only desirable when it can identify K_2 effectively, i.e. the test is more likely to reject H_0 when $|K_2|$ is larger. We will show this by simulation. Suppose the significance level of the hypothesis testing is $\alpha = 0.05$, the power of the test is the probability of the test statistic (likelihood ratio) larger than $\chi_{0.95}^2(1) = 3.841$. The following summarizes the specification of the simulation:

- $K = 40$ (fixed)
- $K_2 \in \left\{ \begin{array}{l} -40, -32, -24, -16, -8, \\ 0, 8, 16, 24, 32, 40 \end{array} \right\}$
- Number of players = 200
- Initial ratings of the players: randomized between 1,000 and 2,000
- Number of games played = 10,000
- Pairing: All-meet-all, with some players pair up more frequently to mimic reality

K_2	$P_{H_1}(\text{Reject } H_0)$: % of $\lambda_n > 3.841$
-40	1.000
-32	0.999
-24	0.988
-16	0.792
-8	0.262
0	0.054
8	0.275
16	0.743
24	0.979
32	0.998
40	1.000

Table 2: Simulation of λ_n , power of the test.

For each value of K_2 , we used 1000 different seeds to get the distribution of λ_n . Table 2 summarizes the result. We can see that the power curve is standard, i.e. the higher the $|K_2|$, the more likely we can reject H_0 .

4. Performance on Simulated Data

This section demonstrates that the proposed method effectively detects pairwise strengths and improves prediction and estimation. We generated datasets for two scenarios:

- Time-varying player strengths, no pairwise advantages (transitivity holds)
- Time-varying strengths, non-zero pairwise advantages (transitivity violated)

To balance coverage and computational cost, we simulated 50,000 games among 10 players, covering all 45 possible pairs. This ensures sufficient data per pair. We will test the significance of the intransitivity, compare the performance of the classic Elo rating system and P-Elo in terms of accuracy, area under the curve (AUC), and their ability to recover true time-varying winning probabilities. Additionally, we will demonstrate the advantage of using P-Elo for betting against classic Elo, which is the Hypothetical Betting Scheme explained below.

Hypothetical Betting Scheme P-Elo improves winning probabilities by incorporating pairwise components, but this does not always lead to better binary predictions. When players' ratings differ greatly (e.g., 90% vs. 80% chance), or when there are many possible pairs (e.g., 200 players \rightarrow 19,900 pairs), accuracy or AUC may not reflect small probability improvements. Likelihood metrics are more informative but less intuitive.

To evaluate performance, we propose a hypothetical betting scheme. Assume a bookmaker X sets odds using Classic Elo, while a bettor Y uses P-Elo probabilities. Y bets only when P-Elo identifies "good deals" — cases where X's odds underestimate true probabilities. Profits are simulated using bootstrap sampling: from the test set, Y randomly selects 1,000 games to bet \$1 on (duplicates increase the bet), and this process is repeated 10,000 times to generate a profit distribution.

In our four scenarios with 50,000 games each, the first 40,000 games train the model, and betting occurs on the remaining 10,000 games. This approach quantifies the advantage of P-Elo over Classic Elo in a straightforward, interpretable way, without implying real-world gambling relevance.

4.1 Evidence of intransitivity

Scenario	A: log-likelihood under Elo	B: log-likelihood under P-Elo	$\lambda_n = -2(A - B)$
Transitivity holds	-20761.07	-20761.04	0.06
Transitivity violated	-22696.80	-19386.55	6620.53

Table 3: Test statistic of both scenarios

When transitivity holds, the maximum likelihood estimate (MLE) for the classic Elo system was $K_{MLE} = 13.7$, with a log-likelihood of -20761.07 . For P-Elo, the MLE $(K, K_2)_{MLE} = (13.7186, -0.0719)$ gave a log-likelihood of -20761.04 . The test statistic from equation (22) is $-2(-20761.07 + 20761.04) = 0.06$. At a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, corresponding to $\chi_{0.95}^2(1) = 3.841$, and considering $0.06 < 3.841$, we do not reject the null hypothesis. This indicates K_2 is not significantly different from 0, so there are no pairwise strengths, and the transitivity assumption holds. When transitivity violated, the classic Elo MLE was $K_{MLE} = 11.87$ with log-likelihood -22696.80 , while P-Elo $(K, K_2)_{MLE} = (11.56, 17.1)$ gave a log-likelihood of -19386.55 . The test statistic is $-2(-22696.80 + 19386.55) = 6620.53$. Since $6620.53 > 3.841$, we reject the null hypothesis. This shows K_2 is significantly different from 0, indicating the presence of pairwise strengths and that the transitivity assumption does not hold for this dataset.

4.2 Prediction performance: Accuracy, AUC, Hypothetical Betting Scheme

Transitivity holds	Accuracy	AUC
Elo	0.8291	0.9125
P-Elo	0.8290	0.9125

Table 4: Model performance comparison when transitivity holds

Transitivity violated	Accuracy	AUC
Elo	0.8172	0.8973
P-Elo	0.8483	0.9263

Table 5: Model performance comparison when transitivity violated

In this section, we use the first 40,000 games (80%) of the dataset for both scenarios as the training set to estimate the best K or (K, K_2) , then predict game results on the remaining 20%. When transitivity holds, the log-likelihoods of both models were nearly identical, so similar prediction performance is expected, see table 4. When transitivity violated, since P-Elo's log-likelihood is significantly higher than classic Elo's, its estimated probabilities are more accurate, resulting in better binary predictions, as shown in table 5. This improvement comes from including pairwise strength components. However, significant gains occur only when the same player pairs appear frequently in the dataset; with a large player pool, improvements in accuracy and AUC may be limited.

Hypothetical Betting Scheme

Figure 1: Hypothetical Betting Scheme (Left: Transitivity holds; Right: Transitivity violated)

The left distribution shows that P-Elo provides no advantage over classic Elo when there are no pairwise strengths, so the betting strategy breaks even. In contrast, the right distribution demonstrates that when pairwise strengths exist, P-Elo outperforms classic Elo, and the betting strategy consistently generates profits, achieving a 100% success rate in this case.

4.3 Recovering the winning probabilities

When transitivity holds, both models can recover winning probabilities well, see figure 2 at the end of the paper. When transitivity violated, the winning probabilities recovery by classic Elo rating is not as effective as P-Elo rating, which is shown in figure 3 and 4.

5. Real-life examples: Sumo Wrestling, MMA, StarCraft II and Large Language Models

Sumo Wrestling

- 204 player
- 31013 matches
- 5696 different match ups

Sumo is a traditional Japanese sport where two wrestlers (rikishi) compete in a circular ring (dohyo). Matches begin with salt-throwing rituals and end when one wrestler forces the other out of the ring or touches the ground with any part of the body other than their feet. Matches require power, balance, and technique, and can last from a few seconds to several minutes. Certain wrestler pairs exhibit specific pairwise strengths due to style, physical attributes, experience, psychology, and training. The Grand Sumo Tournament has six seasons (basho) per year—January, March, May, July, September, and November—with one exception in March 2011. There are 500–1,000 active wrestlers per season, divided into six divisions. Top division wrestlers (Makunouchi and Juryo) compete in 15 matches per season. Match data for the top division from July 2001 to March 2019 include 31,013 matches among 204 wrestlers, accounting for any name changes (shikona). Data were obtained from sumo-hositori.com.

Mixed Martial Arts (MMA)

- 500 frequent players
- 5181 matches
- 4964 different match ups

MMA is a full-contact sport where fighters face each other less frequently than in sumo. This makes it an interesting case for studying pairwise strengths. We used a Kaggle dataset and included the top 500 fighters based on match frequency, noting that matches could pair frequent with non-frequent fighters.

StarCraft II

- 566 players
- 37215 matches
- 3313 different match ups

StarCraft II is a real-time strategy game with one-versus-one matches and three asymmetric races: Terran (balanced, adaptable), Protoss (powerful but costly units), and Zerg (rapid production, territorial control). These differences create complex player interactions, making it ideal for testing rating models beyond transitive strength assumptions. The dataset includes 374,794 games from January 1, 2011, to December 31, 2016. After filtering for player pairs with at least seven matches, the refined dataset has 37,215 games among 566 players.

Large Language Models (LLMs)

- 64 models
- 39716 matches
- 1245 different match ups

LLMs have been ranked using Bradley-Terry models, but pairwise strengths can compromise ranking accuracy. Our goal is to investigate transitivity among LLMs. The Kaggle dataset used here removes draws for direct application of our methods, though draws could be incorporated into P-Elo in future work.

	Sumo	MMA	SC2	LLM
Log-likelihood under Elo	-20062.68	-3506.473	-24268.77	-24967.97
Log-likelihood under P-Elo	-20017.81	-3505.088	-24105.38	-24953.04
λ_n	89.74	2.77	326.78	29.86

Table 6: Likelihood Ratio Test statistic on Real-life datasets

Using significance level $\alpha = 0.05$, we have rejection region $\lambda_n \geq \chi_{0.95}^2(1) = 3.841$. In Sumo Wrestling, we observe strong intransitivity. Mixed Martial Arts exhibit weak intransitivity, as we are unable to reject H_0 . StarCraft II shows the strongest intransitivity among all four domains, while Large Language Models display only mild intransitivity.

For sumo wrestling, MMA, and LLM datasets, we used the first 80% of games/comparisons as the training set to estimate the best K or (K, K_2) , then predicted outcomes on the remaining 20%.

Sumo Wrestling: The MLE for P-Elo yielded $K_2 = 18.83$, significantly different from 0, but accuracy (0.5961) and AUC (0.6492) showed only slight improvement over classic Elo (accuracy 0.5959, AUC 0.6472). This is likely due to the limited number of matchups between similarly rated wrestlers. With 204 wrestlers and 31,013 games, there are 5,696 possible pairings, which is relatively high for the number of games, making accuracy and AUC less suitable measures of model performance.

MMA: The dataset included 5,181 games among 1,755 fighters (500 frequent fighters). Only a few matchups appeared multiple times, with most occurring once, so pairwise strengths had little impact. Consequently, K_2 estimates for P-Elo were unreliable, and accuracy and AUC remained similar to Elo (Elo: 0.5502/0.5657, P-Elo: 0.5473/0.5633).

StarCraft II: After filtering for frequent pairings, the dataset included 37,215 matches among 566 players, representing 3,313 unique matchups. Each matchup appeared at least seven times. P-Elo showed a high $K_2 = 41.11$, indicating strong pairwise effects. Accuracy and AUC improved modestly over Elo (Elo: 0.6259/0.6801, P-Elo: 0.6288/0.6840), reflecting the presence of intransitivity.

LLMs: The dataset included 64 models and 39,716 comparisons, with 1,245 unique pairings. Likelihood ratio tests indicate significant pairwise strengths and violations of transitivity. In 11,915 test comparisons, 350 predictions differed between classic Elo and P-Elo. Classic Elo correctly predicted 165 of these, while P-Elo achieved 185 correct predictions. For the remaining comparisons, predictions aligned despite differences in winning probabilities (Elo: 0.6445/0.7013, P-Elo: 0.6462/0.7018).

Figure 5: Hypothetical betting scheme for real life datasets

P-Elo shows slightly better accuracy and AUC for StarCraft II, where intransitivity is strong. For MMA, pairwise strengths have little effect due to weak intransitivity, so P-Elo does not improve predictions. Although sumo wrestling and LLM comparisons also exhibit strong intransitivity, P-Elo provides limited gains over classic models. To evaluate P-Elo’s advantage, we applied the hypothetical betting scheme. In sumo wrestling, the strategy yields profits 94.2% of the time, with a mean profit of \$60.12 (standard deviation (SD) \$37.92). In MMA, P-Elo underperforms, making profits only 32.65% of the time, with a mean loss of \$14.35. For StarCraft II, P-Elo achieves profits 99.36% of the time, with a mean of \$94.73 (SD \$37.38), reflecting improved predictive performance. In LLM comparisons, P-Elo consistently outperforms classic Elo, achieving profits 100% of the time, with a mean of \$275.16 (SD \$59.77), likely due to a smaller pool of models and a larger number of games.

6. Conclusion

We introduced a simple extension of the Elo rating system, combined with a likelihood ratio test, to detect intransitivity. The P-Elo model estimates both player strengths and pairwise interaction strengths. In frequent matchups, pairwise strength plays a bigger role in outcome predictions. By relaxing the transitivity assumption, this model improves winning probability estimation.

Applying it to real-world datasets, we found that in games like StarCraft 2, sumo wrestling, and MMA, transitivity can be assessed using the likelihood ratio test within the Elo framework. A similar test can be implemented with the Bradley-Terry model, but it requires a small player pool and many games for valid results. The P-Elo system offers more accurate predictions, especially when matchups occur frequently. Our simulations show that with a small player pool and many games, P-Elo provides higher accuracy and AUC.

Appendix: Figures

Figure 2: Recovery of probabilities using classic Elo rating on dataset when transitivity hold

Games

Figure 3: Recovery of probabilities using classic Elo rating on dataset when transitivity violated

Figure 4: Recovery of probabilities using P-Elo rating on dataset when transitivity violated

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